

A STUDY OF THE IMPACT OF SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT ON THE COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF ARAB POTASH FIRM IN JORDAN VIA SOCIAL MEDIA WEBSITES

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Abstract

This study uses social media to investigate how a Jordanian Arab potash company's supply chain affects its competitive advantage and customer happiness. Managers from a wide range of administrative specializations make up the study's population. As the firm's primary resource, customers are the focal point of any effort to improve the Arab potash firm in Jordan, therefore understanding the effects of supply chain management is crucial. Research is still needed at Arab potash companies so that they can better serve their customers. Considering this, the basic goal of this research is to develop a theoretical framework for analyzing the key aspects that may affect the primary impact of supply chain management on boosting competitive advantages and customer satisfaction in an Arab potash enterprise in Jordan. The report concludes with a detailed illustration of the proposed research model.

Keywords: Supply Chain Management, Competitive Advantages, Customer Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

The dynamic and competitive landscape in which modern institutions conduct their day-to-day business and operations, coupled with the ever-evolving nature of information technology and the ever-evolving nature of client needs, necessitates constant reorganization and reinvention on the part (Xiaole & Piscunova, 2022). Industrial organizations had to adapt to new ideas like on-demand services and manufacturing, consumer empowerment, and long-term partnerships with suppliers, all of which helped them enhance their operations, address their primary challenges, and create better final goods and services (Winkler et al., 2022).

Supply chain management is a relatively new idea that has evolved as a means for businesses to deal with issues arising from their immediate surroundings (Aityassine et al., 2022). Several of the relationships in a supply chain indicate practices in which internal and external roles are shared by participants. Achieving competitive advantage needs a long-term relationship between the organization and its suppliers, and the success of this chain depends on integration, involvement, and coordination between the parties involved in marketing, production, supply,

selling, and shipping (Manfredi & Capik, 2022). Simplifying the description of production-related tasks such as the supply of basic goods to the factory and the distribution of finished products by taking advantage and partnering with individuals and organizations have strategic and operational capabilities to help them to achieve significant continuous benefits. Furthermore, the logistics organization is keen to supply a professional flow of items that keeps manufacturing running in the most efficient way possible, taking into account costs, service levels, and other crucial logistical concerns. This has been shown to be the case (Xiaole & Piscunova, 2022). With the advent of new communication technologies, the importance of this idea expanded, notably in the realm of marketing (Al-Hawary & Al-Syasneh, 2020). Several benefits and advantages emerged when businesses began integrating social communication into their interactions with customers and clients, including streamlined processes for sharing information and achieving common goals. Maintaining direct linkages and communication between the factory and the ultimate consumer was made easier by social networks and social media, which also made it simpler for marketers to discover client preferences and issues (Zeng et al., 2022). Furthermore, it was possible to gain instant feedback from them, which improved the enterprises' adaptability and speed in responding to customers' demands. It enabled businesses to maintain long-term agreements with their suppliers, which strengthened the bonds between the two parties (Ambrogio et al., 2022).

The concept of social media in supply chain management is gaining popularity among academics, consultants, and managers (Pimenta et al., 2022; Kraus et al., 2022). Many companies now understand that social media supply chain management is essential to gaining an edge in crowded markets for their goods and services. The manufacturing industry is extremely competitive due to rising global competition and consumer expectations (Sodhi et al., 2019). In addition, the product life cycle is getting shorter, new products are being introduced at a faster rate, and customers continue to demand higher quality, faster responses to their needs, and higher dependability of goods and services as the new competitive environment becomes more global and technology-oriented. Markets in Jordan went from being monopolized to becoming free-for-alls as different types of businesses developed and as the number of industrial firms grew. As competition among these businesses heated up, the once monopolized firms saw their market shares erode. However, the industry as a whole was hurt by the fact that some of its suppliers had a rocky relationship with the market, making it difficult for them to meet consumer demand and, as a result, drive down prices. As a result, the research topic became determining whether or not supply chain management via social media may have an effect on the operations, rivalry, and market share of these businesses.

The purpose of this research is to provide a conceptual framework for studying the possible effects of supply chain management on the competitive advantage and customer satisfaction of an Arab potash enterprise in Jordan by means of online social networking. It is suggested that this model be evaluated in further studies with the goal of improving the Arab potash firm in Jordan as the unit of analysis. In order to put the framework to the test in a real-world setting and verify the findings of prior studies about the relationship between study variables, the researchers plan to create a survey for users or organizations to complete in the near future.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Supply chain management

Companies in the modern global economy must adopt a wide range of strategies to satisfy their clients' needs. One of the most popular approaches involves fostering a more adaptable approach to operations and activities, as modern businesses place a premium on maximizing the efficiency with which they respond to clients' requests (Al-Hawary, 2013). Supply chains need to be adaptable in order to survive in today's dynamic economic climate (Akn A. et al., 2022). This is due to the growing complexity of client requirements, which includes factors like the wide variety of products offered and their manufacturing to meet individual needs. Supply chains have risen to prominence due to the competitive advantage gained via cost leadership and the presence of novel, substantial difficulties and opportunities in the interactions between the firm and its customers and suppliers (Akn A. et al., 2022). Successful supply chain management will undoubtedly reduce costs for each customer, as it entails managing the flow of information, materials, services, and funds through any activity in a way that improves operational efficiency, and as it also involves introducing new tools or changing or modifying existing methods. Organizations who do the best job of managing their supply chains also have the lowest risk and the highest value-added and profit margins (Olatunji et al., 2019).

Researchers and others with an interest have proposed a number of definitions of "supply chain management," and study of these definitions reveals several areas of convergence (Mardani et al., 2020). Supply chain management refers to the process wherein a company ensures the smooth flow of resources (including raw materials, components, information, and currency) from their suppliers to the company and ultimately to the end consumer (Van G. et al., 2019). The following is the definition of supply chain management as given by the Council of Supply Chain Management Specialists: Supply chain management encompasses the planning and management of all activities related to the procurement of materials and other logistical management activities, including collaboration and coordination with suppliers, brokers, other service providers, and customers. This includes anything that has to do with making and sending out goods or services to customers (Ramirez-Pea et al., 2020). One definition of supply chain management is the coordination of a company's procurement of raw materials, manufacture, assembly, distribution, and final delivery of finished goods in response to customer orders (Karim et al., 2020).

Supply chain management is defined by the International Supply Chain Authority as "the coordination of an organization's actions — from sourcing raw materials to delivery to clients — to maximize the value created for those customers and other stakeholders along the supply chain" (Dwivedi et al., 2020). According to Madhani (2022), the term "supply chain relationship management" refers to the process of proactively moving resources, products, and funds from suppliers through an organization's activities and on to the final consumer. These connections can be exemplified by the provider's partnership, which emphasizes open communication, trust, and shared goals achieved through various forms of collaboration (Sharma et al., 2022). According to Ahmad H. et al. (2021), value for the customer is increased

through the management of two-way relationships between suppliers and buyers; he also noted that, if transactions are handled independently, the objective is to minimize costs, and it is, of course, the buyer who determines which supply chains offer him the best combination of price and quality. Therefore, satisfying customers is the key to the company's longevity. Consequently, it is clear that the primary goal of the aforementioned definitions is to gain an advantage by increasing the market value of all outputs (Hanandeh A. et al., 2022). However, supply chain management as a discipline has barely begun to develop.

2.2 Social Media Websites

Organizations are beginning to consider how to take advantage of these tools to support their activities and facilitate their work as the concept of social media has entered people's lives and affected people's operations and activities in general. There is no doubt that the elements and components of the supply chain based on relation As social media marketing expanded its success, the concept of supply chain management emerged to capitalize on the trend (Barakat S., 2022).

In this regard, the emergence of social media and its capacity to form user networks presents fresh chances to establish novel distribution channels (Changchit et al., 2022). Producers can refine target group definition and develop more effective marketing strategies by using social media to learn more about their customers' social and demographic characteristics (Changchit et al., 2022). On the other side, the use of social media can be constrained by the public's conception of these sites as purely ad-free social hubs (Creevey et al., 2022). This research uses a fresh approach to online supply chain management by focusing on the potential of social media. Using online social media as a case study, this study aims to better understand how customers perceive and react to contemporary supply chains.

Supply chain management involves the effective and efficient flow of resources from the point of origin to the point of consumption. This includes demand planning, forecasting, purchasing, production, assembly, distribution, revenue management, and more (Pratapa et al., 2022). One of the most efficient methods for businesses to boost efficiency is by implementing supply chain management strategies. An administration of supply chain activities and enhancement of business performance call for better planning and management of operations in areas including: material planning, inventory management, production capacity planning, and logistical support services to customers. Supply chain processes reflect the many linkages between their members and the ways in which internal and external functions overlap. Integration, participation, and coordination between the marketing, production, supply, sale, and shipping participants is crucial to the success of this chain since it helps to build competitive advantage (Chen et al., 2022).

The strategic relationship with the supplier, the relationship with the customer, information exchange, information quality, internal processes, and delay are the six characteristics identified by Almajali T. et al. (2022) for supply chain management techniques through social media. Through the systems approach, Shaharudin et al. (2019) have developed a tool to measure supply chain conditioning and management at the level of the concepts of supply chain

management practices, indicating that it consists of dimensions like shared vision and goals, information systems, shared risks and rewards, interoperability, process integration, relationships, and long-lasting supply chain leadership. Recruitment, strategic supplier partnerships, information and technology sharing, active provisioning, continuous process flow, utilizing an internal organizational system, basic capabilities, surplus inventory disposal, supply chain integration, management, customer service, proximity to market, on-demand production, customer relationships, product modularity, and scalability were all highlighted as important by previous research (Heath et al., 2017; Hanandy Z., 2022).

2.3 Competitive Advantages and Customer Satisfaction

Given its definition in terms of the scientific frameworks that it seeks to solve, competitive advantage is a crucial part of every market-facing strategy. Others focused on the significance of the industry structure, while still others approached it from the perspective of the industry analysis process. Recent research into competitive advantage has focused on a new framework: the internal dimension. An organization's competitive advantage is based on a set of unique capabilities that are developed in-house, and the people in charge of those organizations need to be well-versed in those capabilities and invest competitively in them. The ability to interact with external actors from a position of strength, control, and stability is a definition of competitive advantage in the external dimension (Nayak et al., 2021). One way to characterize the significance of a characteristic is by its "competitiveness," which refers to its potential for conflict with third parties. Lowest price, greatest quality, finest service, and most distinctive offering are the four pillars of competitive advantage. Several studies have shown that the lowest cost and differentiation can be a source of competitive advantage (Al-khawaldah et al., 2022; AlTaweel & Al-Hawary, 2021).

According to Porter, a company has a competitive advantage when it has the ability to lower its costs or is unique in some aspects that the customer considers to be of great value, and this advantage arises when the company discovers new methods that are more effective than those used by competitors. According to Hanandeh A. et al. (2022), a company's competitive advantage is its capacity to establish a commanding position in relation to its rivals, while Hammouri Q. et al. (2022) competitive advantage expands to incorporate strategic decisions about the markets in which the company will operate. The company's success can be attributed to the value it has brought to its clients. Thus, it can take the form of lower pricing in comparison to rivals' prices, with similar advantages, or by delivering individual benefits in the product, proving that modern competition is predicated on a rapid response to shifting market needs. Companies today are actively seeking out ways to distinguish themselves in their respective markets and industries. As a result, they expend considerable work in looking for evidence that backs up their study and ultimately helps them remain competitive and operational. The accelerated activities along the linkages in the supply chain of which it is a part are likely one of the most important reasons for its competitiveness. In an effort to assure the long-term success of enterprises, this research seeks to fortify ties between organizations at every stage of the supply chain in order to facilitate more rapid and efficient communication and data sharing.

3. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The focus of this study is on the theoretical framework, which is derived from past research in the field. In this study, we focused on studying the impact of three variables of supply chain management on enhancing the competitive advantages which represented by (Quality, and Cost) and customer satisfaction which represented through (increasing customers' demands, and decreasing negative complaints) in Arab potash firm in Jordan. The following image depicts the proposed model.

Figure1. Model Concept of the impact of supply chain management on competitive advantages and customers' satisfaction Adopted from (Al-Nawafah Et al., 2022).

It is proposed that future study taking into consideration this model especially in the potash sector in Jordan. The researchers anticipate developing a survey in the near future for users or organizations to fill out in order to test the framework practically and confirm the results of previous studies regarding the impact of supply chain management on competitive advantages and customers' satisfaction.

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